

ENTREPRENEUR - THE OWNER OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND THE SUBJECT OF THE ECONOMIC PROCESS

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Abstract. The article examines the role of the entrepreneur as an economic entity and intellectual capital in social production and the service sector. Theoretically, it outlines the essence of intangible intellectual capital and its role in the development of entrepreneurial activity. It also explores entrepreneurial abilities, which are expressed in all aspects of human productive activity and reflect the level of intellectual capital.

Keywords: entrepreneur, economic order, economic process, subject, entrepreneurial product, profit, inactive and intangible intellectual capital, risk, efficiency.

The entrepreneurial activity in the republic at both macro and microeconomic levels, as well as the sustainable development of the national economy, depend on the level of provision of labor resources with jobs and the ability to supply the population with necessary raw materials for food and industrial sectors.

Our President Sh. Mirziyoyev declared 2018 the "Year of Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies," highlighting the lack of measures to save state resources and entrepreneurs' time, the need to privatize inefficient and unprofitable enterprises, and the necessity to transition to market mechanisms for financing production with broad involvement of the private sector.

Consequently, the creation of necessary organizational, legal, and economic conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in our republic is being

continuously improved. The development of our national economy based on market economy requirements is an economic system founded on entrepreneurship, and the management of its effective implementation is based on state regulation and market economic mechanisms.

In a market economy, the entrepreneur serves as the main factor in the production process and becomes the primary subject of the economic process as an individual. The main task of the market economy process is to fully satisfy the needs of society members, which requires people to pay attention to the following requirements:

- that in a market economy, the market is a saturated market, satisfying all the needs of people while continuously developing, taking into account its changes based on internal and external factors;

- In market conditions, every entrepreneur should focus on independently ensuring production, consumption, and obtaining necessary income based on specific forms, as well as satisfying consumer demand.

The economic process in market conditions is not a novelty for society, but arises as a result of people's entrepreneurial activities. As a result of people's active participation in the economic process, the following can be achieved:

- production and satisfaction of consumer demand for products necessary to meet production and consumer needs;

- Manufacturing entrepreneurs must ensure that they receive a certain level of profit and income from the manufactured products based on the exchange of goods in the consumer market.

Achieving this depends on economic regulation in a market economy. The economic order is linked to entrepreneurs and employees of their enterprises receiving income, participating in the economic process, allocating funds in accordance with the volume of goods produced, and freely purchasing the produced goods.

Economic order represents a person's participation in the production process as a result of labor and the provision of certain services. The presence of economic order in the economic process ensures the formation of economic equality in the economic system, that is, in a market economy based on various forms of ownership.

In conclusion, it can be said that the economic process is organized by people and, as a result of specific actions between them, is manifested in the production of goods necessary for society and its members. The quality of labor of individuals participating in the economic process, including entrepreneurs, depends on the professional level, theoretical knowledge, and skills of people employed in production.

Entrepreneurial activity is interconnected with business entities, as well as financial, banking, and tax departments, which are state institutions. Entrepreneurs must strive to utilize effective methods in managing these relationships.

An entrepreneur participating in the economic process must consider consumers' desires, interests, preferences, and product pricing when planning and implementing their production activities. In a market economy, only consumers can provide an economic assessment of entrepreneurial activity. The economic situation of a manufacturing entrepreneur is linked to consumer demands, which constantly evolve and improve. Simultaneously, manufacturing entrepreneurs should strive to shape production and economic relations between producers and consumers by studying the consumer market and producing high-quality, affordable products that meet consumer demands.

Factors influencing consumers by entrepreneurs

Figure 1. Factors influencing consumers by entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurs should organize their production constantly taking into account competitive conditions in the consumer market. A manufacturing entrepreneur, while continuously improving the production process to maintain their position in the consumer market, can influence consumers through the factors shown in Figure

In market conditions, an entrepreneur engaged in production represents the main active subject in society, while in their entrepreneurial activity, the consumer is the primary subject. The entrepreneur's activity can be effective only on the basis of establishing proper economic relations between them.

An entrepreneur's ability to carry out their business activities and produce and deliver consumer goods that meet market demands depends on the level of utilization of highly skilled workers.

At the same time, each entrepreneur, as an economic entity, has their own economic interests. While the economic interest of an entrepreneur as a production entity consists of reducing production costs and obtaining high profits, the interest of workers in receiving high wages is constantly growing. Consequently, without creating the necessary conditions for production and addressing the contradictions between the producing entrepreneurial entity and the workers engaged in production regarding efforts to increase wages in economic relations, the entrepreneurial activity will not be effective. Therefore, entrepreneurs can prevent existing conflicts or ensure their resolution by inviting qualified workers to work as much as possible and involving them in business management to ensure production development. This approach allows entrepreneurs to achieve their goals by mitigating or resolving existing contradictions.

One of the methods for ensuring workers' economic interest by an entrepreneur is expressed in aligning their economic interests with those of the entrepreneur. The entrepreneur sees the growth of wages in connection with the growth of their own income. Consequently, the growth in efficiency of entrepreneurial activity should be directly proportional to the increase in wages of the production workers employed. Based on the above theoretical analysis, the following conclusion can be drawn: Effectiveness is the result of cooperative labor, the growth of which is reflected in the level of utilization of innovative equipment and technologies in production, the increase in labor productivity, the efficient use of working time, and the improvement in the quality of labor.

In our opinion, the effectiveness of entrepreneurial activity in a market economy should be manifested in the reduction of labor and material costs per unit of output. In a market economy, the development of human entrepreneurial activity

or the capitalization of the workforce involved in production has special socio-economic significance. In a market economy, intellectual capital, as part of active capital expenditures, is expressed in the costs of intangible capital.

In the process of economic development based on market economy relations, labor force, raw materials, and means of production are necessary for production, which is expressed in the capitalization of human resources.

Intellectual capital is a special form of capital that, while having a certain monetary value, participates in organizing the production process through its business acumen. Intellectual capital embodied in a person can be expressed in two forms. In comparison to simple labor involved in the production of material goods, intellectual capital represents labor that is more efficient and profitable in terms of production volume, quality, cost, and overall product effectiveness.

While not denying its role in the socio-economic development of society, non-active intellectual capital is also expressed in its level of effectiveness and value. This is reflected in the training of qualified specialists and workers with professional skills, ensuring the required level of social living standards for the population through medical services, and creating conditions for recreation.

The role of intangible intellectual capital in the development of entrepreneurial activity should not be underestimated. Intangible intellectual capital does not create tangible wealth itself, but actively participates in transforming manufactured goods into capital by ensuring the movement of created products in the commodity market and delivering goods to consumers in the consumer market.

At the same time, it actively participates in organizing effective management of the production process to achieve specific set goals. The essence of intangible intellectual capital takes on special significance in a market economy. In a market economy, intangible intellectual capital plays a crucial role in effectively organizing the human production process and ensuring the efficiency of entrepreneurship under free competition conditions, while maintaining constant

secrecy regarding methods of achieving economic success in the production process.

An entrepreneur's intellectual capital can consist not only of intellectual capital created by them but also of intellectual capital they have purchased. Intellectual entrepreneurial capital used in the entrepreneurial process has a broad meaning and represents the result of technological production related to organizing the production process, manufacturing new high-quality, inexpensive goods in the form of value.

In conclusion, it can be said that in a market economy, the organization of entrepreneurial activity and ensuring its effectiveness cannot be carried out without the involvement of intellectual capital. Thus, in market conditions, entrepreneurial capital consists of tangible and intangible intellectual capital. Tangible capital is associated with the organization of entrepreneurship and is expressed in the form of valuable means of production, raw materials, and labor. Intangible intellectual assets, while not having monetary value, are embodied in the entrepreneur's ability to organize entrepreneurial activity.

Entrepreneurial ability is expressed in the entrepreneur's organization of the production process based on the requirements of a market economy, establishing production that is effective and resistant to free market competition. The increase in a person's level of intellectual capitalization depends not only on the acquisition of theoretical, fundamental, and practical knowledge but also on the application of this knowledge to practical experience.

For a person to become an entrepreneur who meets market conditions, they must have a deep understanding of the organizational, economic, and legal aspects of production. Additionally, they should not fear risks associated with the production process, be able to prevent existing risks, and have a willingness to take calculated risks. These qualities ensure their formation as an entrepreneur.

A person's entrepreneurial ability is expressed in all aspects of their

production activity and reflects their level of intellectual capital. A person's intellectual capital represents the development of their abilities related to entrepreneurial activity. The intellectual ability of a person:

- human intellectual capital in organizing entrepreneurial activity and producing goods necessary for the consumer market;

- in implementing entrepreneurial ideas related to the organization of entrepreneurial activity;

- in attracting innovative investors with scientific and innovative achievements to organize entrepreneurial activity;

- is expressed in organizing effective entrepreneurial activity based on innovative ideas.

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